

EXAMINATION OF THE INTERFACE STRENGTH OF HYBRID, OVERMOULDED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE PARTS

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid material combinations offer unique advantages in terms of material properties, cost efficiency and design. Endless fibre reinforced plastics are used nowadays in various fields of applications. However, these structural high-performance materials are seldom used for mass production parts and have design restrictions. Contrarily, short fibre reinforced plastics are commonly used in parts produced with high rates and short cycle times for example by injection moulding. With this manufacturing technology, complex shapes can be realised. This paper focuses on the combination of endless and short fibre reinforced materials to combine the advantages of both. As a result, structural cost-efficient composite parts can be realized which are produced in short time and with high production rates. In this study, carbon fibre polyether ether ketone (CF PEEK) is used. PEEK is a thermoplastic material with high structural mechanical properties and good temperature resistance. In addition to that, it is biocompatible. It is therefore used in aerospace or for medical applications, for example.

In this paper, different test methods are used and compared to examine the interface strength of endless unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced PEEK inserts (uCF-PEEK) which are overmoulded by short carbon fibre reinforced PEEK (sCF-PEEK) moulding material. A special test body is developed to account for the case of complete overmoulding. The influence of sample preparation steps such as pre-heating is examined. It is found that pre-heating of uCF-PEEK inserts up to temperatures well above the glass transition temperature of PEEK is required in order to achieve sufficient interface strength. Examinations of the interface indicate cohesive interface formation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Within the past few years, carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics were increasingly used in various fields of applications. In contrast to thermosets, they can be processed in shorter cycle times and in higher numbers [1-3]. Furthermore, thermoplastics are re-meltable and can be welded [4]. Another aspect refers to recycling which is one of the main topics of the present and also for the future. Whereas the recycling of thermosets is quite difficult, thermoplastic materials can be recycled much easier [1, 4, 5]. However for both carbon fibre reinforced material types, the raw material cost can be a competitive disadvantage [4]. This motivates the need for alternative solutions for the development of structural composite parts.

The thermoplastic material PEEK has a unique combination of properties such as high temperature stability, excellent impact properties, high structural mechanical properties and high solvent resistance [6, 7]. According to Holmes it is suitable for “any applications where weight, cost, efficiency, or performance are critical engineering requirements“ [2]. Hybrid material combinations offer the possibility of using specific advantages of both materials [8] and enable significant cost savings. This paper focuses on the hybrid combination of injection moulded short carbon fibre reinforced polyether ether ketone (sCF-PEEK) with unidirectional endless carbon fibre reinforced polyether ether ketone (uCF-PEEK) only where needed. As a consequence, parts based on this concept are very cost efficient while still having excellent mechanical properties. The injection moulding process is well suited for mass production, excellent repeatability, short cycle times and automation [9]. Complex shapes can be

moulded easily. However, injected parts without insert typically have lower structural mechanical properties compared to continuous fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) [10] due to fibre discontinuity, random fibre distributions and orientations. However, the disadvantage of using continuous FRP lays in the limitation of formability [11]. The hybrid manufacturing process of overmoulding combines advantages, which one part cannot fulfil [2, 12, 13] so that complex parts can be produced cost efficiently [14].

The relatively expensive uCF-PEEK material is used to transfer forces along specific load paths only where needed. Simultaneously, the freedom in the design of complex shaped geometries is maintained due to the overmoulded sCF-PEEK material. To ensure the functionality of hybrid thermoplastic composite parts, the adhesion between the uCF-PEEK component and the overmoulded sCF-PEEK material is crucial and has to be verified. A new test body is developed to account for an application case of complete overmoulded thermoplastic composite parts and to further investigate this new promising technology.

Pre-heating of the inserts promotes the formation of a strong cohesive interface. However, if the heat transfer from the molten mass to the insert is insufficient, no cohesive interface is formed. In this case, the interface can rather be described as adhesive.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Compression shear test

The compression shear test has the advantage of favourable stress distribution in contrast to the tension shear test [15]. In addition to that, the compression stiffness of the two materials used is more similar than their corresponding tension stiffness. Thus, a more homogeneous stress distribution in the contact area is expected. However, one difficulty lays in the precise preparation of the compression shear test samples, as described later.

The tests are performed to characterize the strength of the interface between the uCF-PEEK plates and the overmoulded sCF-PEEK material Victrex PEEK 450CA30 with a carbon fibre mass fraction of 30 % [16, 17]. The uCF-PEEK plate has a fibre volume fraction of about 60 % according to the manufacturer *Haufler Composites GmbH & Co. KG* (Blaubeuren, Germany). Carbon AS4 A fibres are used within the PEEK matrix. Since the formation of a cohesive interface is uncertain, a confocal topography and a contact angle measurement are conducted prior to compression shear testing to characterize adhesion capability.

2.1.1 Confocal topography measurement

To connect two parts with each other, micro mechanical interlocking is one possible mechanism which contributes to adhesive interface strength. To evaluate the interlocking possibility, the surface roughness of uCF-PEEK plates with dimensions of 80 mm x 79.5 mm x 2 mm (length x width x thickness) is optically measured with a confocal topography measurement system from *NanoFocus* at the *Institute for measurement and sensor technology (MTS)* at the *Technical University Kaiserslautern (TUK)*. After cleaning with isopropanol, the topography is analysed by using two different measuring lengths in the centre at the back and the front of the specimen and at each corner at the front. The positions of the measuring lengths in the centre of the specimen are slightly different to prevent measuring at the same spot. The measured lengths are orthogonal to the fibre orientation of the uCF-PEEK plate.

2.1.2 Test procedure

For the production of the compression shear specimens, five uCF-PEEK plates with the dimensions of 80 mm x 79.5 mm x 2 mm (length x width x thickness) are cut out of a bigger plate with a diamond circular saw. The width is orthogonal to the fibre direction and considers the thermal expansion in the pre-heated state of the plate so that they fit in the mould of the injection moulding machine *Arburg 320 S Allrounder 500-150*. The mould has a dimension of 80 mm x 80 mm x 4 mm (length x width x thickness), so that the volume of the insert is half the volume of the mould cavity. All six plates are cleaned with isopropanol. Two inserts are heated in an oven to 200 °C and one is heated to 250 °C.

This temperature is higher than the glass transition temperature of about 143 °C but lower than the melting temperature of PEEK of about 343 °C [16]. Considering the different transfer times, all the pre-heated plates have a temperature of approximately 170 °C just before overmoulding. After manual transfer, two plates at room temperature and four pre-heated plates are overmoulded with sCF-PEEK. Two ovens are used for pre-heating. They are placed near the injection moulding machine to keep transfer time and temperature loss low.

The overmoulding is done with a temperature of 395 °C of the molten material, a mould temperature of 200 °C and an injection pressure of 160 MPa. The holding pressure is 55 MPa. After overmoulding, the specimens are prepared according to ASTM D 695 and ASTM D 3846. Figure 1 illustrates the geometry of the compression shear test specimens on the right. The hybrid plates are cut into stripes with a width of 12.7 mm. A hand milling tool is used to mill the two required grooves into the specimens layer by layer. It is important to ensure that their depth is lower than the thickness of the adherend. Otherwise, the compression strength of the adherend and not the strength of the interface is tested [18]. The ends of the specimens are ground parallel and plane.

Figure 1: Compression shear test set-up (left) and specimen geometry (right)

The compression shear test is done with a *Hydropuls Längszylinder PL 10 kN* from *Instron structural testing systems*. The testing speed is 1 mm/min and the tests are performed at room temperature. The specimens are not clamped by the testing machine. Two small supports with a slightly bigger thickness are clamped and are aligned by a special positioning tool. They are used to apply the compression force only at the specimens' ends. A buckling support is used for the test with teeth at the contact area to the specimen to keep friction forces low. The test set-up is shown in figure 1 on the left.

2.2 Single lap shear test

Specimens are cut out of the uCF-PEEK plate with dimensions of 100 mm x 25 mm x 2 mm (length x width x thickness) and used as inserts in the single lap shear (SLS) overmoulding process. Six of twelve inserts are surface ground with abrasive paper P120 at the overmould area. All inserts are cleaned with isopropanol prior to overmoulding. Their interface area is heated up with a heating plate (IKA C-MAG HP) to 300-320 °C which is far above the glass transition temperature of PEEK but below its melting temperature. Transfer times are below 10 seconds so that cooling is low. The final insert temperature just before overmoulding is more than 260 °C. The overmoulding material is sCF-PEEK (*Akrotek PEEK CF30*) from *Akro-Plastic GmbH* (Niederzissen, Germany) with a fibre mass fraction of 30 % [19] and the injection moulding machine is a *Sumitomo (SHI) DEMAG Systec 100-310*. The inserts are partially overmoulded so that SLS specimens are produced. After manufacturing, aluminium cap strips are applied to decrease bending moments during SLS-testing. The tests are carried out in tension on a *Hydropuls Längszylinder PL 10 kN* from *Instron structural testing systems* with a testing speed of 1 mm/min.

2.3 Cylinder pull-out test

To account for the case of complete overmoulding and to further study the interface strength between uCF- and sCF-PEEK, a special test body is developed. The test body consists of a cylinder which is moulded over a length of 34 mm of the rod insert. The temperature distribution is nearly symmetric so that thermal stresses are evenly distributed [20]. The injection moulding machine *Babyplast type 6/10 PT* is used for the manufacturing of the pull-out specimens. In figure 2, the cylinder pull-out test set-up can be seen on the left and the specimen geometry on the right. An FE-model is built up and the diameter of the cylinder is chosen in that way that no edge effects affect the pull-out behaviour up to a theoretical pull-out force of 10 kN. With this diameter, also the contact area between the cylinder's bottom face and the perforated plate surface of the testing machine is big enough in terms of pressure distribution. To lower the influence of manufacturing defects, the overmoulding length is maximized up to 34 mm so that the maximum injection volume of the Babyplast machine is used.

Figure 2: Cylinder pull-out test set-up (left) and specimen geometry (right)

Five steel rod (cold work steel 1.2210, 115CrV3, Meusberger ejector pin e1710 [21]) and ten uCF-PEEK rod inserts are overmoulded with sCF-PEEK and tested in a special pull-out testing jig. The steel inserts have a rough-ground surface with an average surface finish of 0.4 mm. Of the ten uCF-PEEK inserts, five are inserted without pre-heating. The specimens produced with these inserts at room temperature are referred to as *cold inserts*. The other five inserts are heated up to 290 °C in an oven (*Heraeus RL 200*) after cleaning with isopropanol. Afterwards, they are manually transferred to the injection moulding machine. The specimens with pre-heated inserts are called *hot inserts*. Trials have shown that the target temperature of the oven used is close to the actual temperature of the insert. A heated metal cask is used for the transport of the inserts to decrease the influence of a cooling air stream and to decrease the loss of temperature of the specimens. Transfer time is kept lower than ten seconds so that the temperature of the inserts just before overmoulding is more than 260 °C.

The ten uCF-PEEK inserts are turned from a bigger diameter to its final diameter of 2.5 mm. To properly fix the rod in the mould, its diameter needs to be within a small tolerance range. In the injection moulding machine, the inserts are pushed through small metal parts with centred holes. These parts ensure a proper fixation of the insert during overmoulding and prevent the insert from being pushed through. If the rod diameter is too big, the rod does not fit in the hole of the fixation jigs. If it is too small, there is the danger that the injection pressure pushes the rod out of place. Besides a correct rod diameter, it is important that it is long enough to realize an appropriate fixation in the injection moulding machine. However, it should not be longer than needed due to limited stock, material cost and material savings. After cutting the rods in lengths of 100 mm, two flat faces are ground at the end of the rods so they can be clamped easier in the testing machine. It has to be mentioned that the person in charge has to take care during handling of the hot inserts. Temperature

resistant gloves and pliers have to be provided. The final specimens are demoulded by ejector pins. Sprue and runner are manually cut off with a stationary grinder.

The test is done with a *Hydropuls Längszylinder PL 10 kN* from *Instron structural testing systems*. The testing speed is 0.5 mm/min and the tests are performed at room temperature.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Compression shear test results

3.1.1 Confocal topography measurement results

Figure 3 summarizes the average roughness values R_a (roughness average), R_p (maximum profile peak height) and R_z (average maximum height of profile) with their corresponding standard deviations.

Figure 3: Average and standard deviation of the surface roughness values R_a , R_p and R_z of the uCF-PEEK plate

To illustrate the surface topography, figure 4 shows an image of a scanning electron microscope (SEM) with a magnification of 50 (left) and 250 (right). The images are taken with a cathode voltage of 20 kV.

Figure 4: SEM image of the surface of the uCF-PEEK plate

The results indicate that small pores and cavities exist on the surface. The fibre orientation is visible, due to the high fibre volume fraction. To examine the influence of a pre-heating process step on the surface roughness, a uCF-PEEK plate is heated in an oven at 250 °C for about one hour. The roughness values R_a , R_p and R_z of the pre-heated uCF-PEEK plate are not significantly different than the corresponding values of the non-heated plate. The pre-heating temperature of up to 250 °C is

above the glass transition temperature of approximately 143 °C of the PEEK matrix but still far below its melting temperature of approximately 343 °C [16]. At this pre-heating temperature only micro Brownian motion of molecule chains is relevant. In contrast to macro Brownian motion, which occurs at higher temperatures, there is no movement of chain centres of mass. Therefore, the surface topology of the uCF-PEEK insert is not significantly changed.

3.1.2 Results of test procedure

Several difficulties and problems arise during sample preparation:

- **Curvature:** After overmoulding, the hybrid plates show a curvature which is a result of thermal stresses which arise during cooling. The sCF- und uCF-PEEK materials have different thermal expansion coefficients so that their contraction is also different.
- **Pre-stressing:** Due to the curvature of the specimens, the interface is pre-stressed during the clamping process which is needed for cutting the specimens and milling the grooves. The buckling support also pre-stresses the specimens due to their curvature. Cutting and milling introduces vibrations which affect the interface.
- **Cooling:** Due to insert pre-heating, less heat has to be transferred from the molten mass to the insert in order to melt the insert surface and to achieve a cohesive interface. On the one hand, the pre-heating temperature of the insert has to be close to its melting temperature to facilitate cohesion. On the other hand, form stability has to be maintained to handle the insert. The pre-heated inserts cool between opening the oven and start the overmoulding. Thus, the transfer of the inserts has to be fast to decrease cooling. The final temperature of the insert depends on pre-heating temperature, transfer time, transfer condition and mould temperature.
- **Plane and parallel specimen ends:** The ends of the specimens have to be plane and parallel to achieve valid test results. However, perfect planarity and parallelism are difficult to achieve.
- **Low matrix content:** The uCF-insert has a fixed fibre volume content of about 60 %. Thus, only little matrix material is located at the insert surface. The molten mass can only build a cohesive interface with the matrix material. Therefore, increasing the matrix content of the insert would contribute to a stronger cohesive interface.

Due to these issues, several specimens fail during preparation so that no statistically relevant results can be achieved in the compression shear test. Examination of the failure surface of the specimens indicates that adhesive failure occurs. The heat transfer from the molten mass to the insert is insufficient to melt the matrix material at the surface of the insert and to form a cohesive interface. It can be concluded that micro mechanical interlocking between uCF-PEEK insert and overmould does not significantly contribute to interface strength.

It can be concluded that all specimens have poor interface strengths. The pre-heating temperature is not high enough to form a cohesive interface and too many process steps contribute to interface weakening. Nevertheless, several parameters which influence the interface strength could be determined with this study. It is necessary to ensure a cohesive interface between uCF-PEEK insert and sCF-PEEK overmould in order to achieve sufficient interface strength. Different test methods with less sample preparation steps have to be established to characterize the interface strength between insert and overmould.

3.2 Single lap shear test results

Figure 5 shows the shear-stress-strain diagrams of the SLS specimens. The term *SLS - rough* represents specimens with partial surface grinding as described above.

Figure 5: Stress-strain diagram of SLS specimens

All specimens fail at the edge of the overlap at the sCF-PEEK parts and not at the interface. This means that the interface strength exceeds the strength of the sCF-PEEK material. At the end of the overlap, stress concentrations are located which contribute to this failure mechanism. This is also why no significant differences in the stress-strain behaviour between SLS specimens with a smooth and a rough overlap surface could be detected.

It can be concluded that a pre-heating temperature of more than 260 °C just before overmoulding is necessary to form a cohesive interface. Below that temperature, the interface strength is poor. A cohesive interface has to be formed so that the two material components are sufficiently connected. Due to stress concentrations at the edge of the overlap and adherend failure, the SLS tests are not applicable for interface strength characterization.

3.3 Cylinder pull-out test results

The test results of the cylinder pull-out test specimens with steel and composite inserts can be seen in figure 6. In this figure, the specimens with steel inserts are shown on the left, with non-heated inserts in the middle and with pre-heated inserts on the right. The number of specimens tested is limited since only few uCF-PEEK rods could be purchased due to availability.

An FE-model is built up in which a perfect bond is assumed between insert and overmould up to first failure. The mean force at first failure of the specimens with steel, non-heated and pre-heated uCF-PEEK inserts is used for the load. The region of high shear stresses is localized in the lower part of the cylinder. For the steel specimens, the shear stress at first failure is approximately 17 MPa. This stress is equal to the maximum stress since first failure corresponds to a complete and sudden failure of the interface of the steel specimens. The shear stress at first failure of the specimens with pre-heated uCF-PEEK inserts is approximately 64 MPa which is 73 % higher than the average shear stress at first failure of the specimens with non-heated inserts (approximately 37 MPa). After first failure of the specimens with composite inserts and a resulting force drop, the force further increases again due to friction and locking mechanisms until it reaches its maximum and total failure occurs. The forces at first failure and the maximum forces for each specimen are listed in table 1.

Figure 6: Pull-out test results of specimens with steel (left), non-heated uCF inserts (middle) and pre-heated uCF-PEEK inserts (right)

Specimen	Force at first failure in N	Maximum force in N
Steel insert 1	508.1	508.1
Steel insert 2	443.4	443.4
Steel insert 3	508.2	508.2
Steel insert 4	438.3	438.3
Steel insert 5	439.3	439.3
Mean value	467.4	467.4
Standard deviation	33.3	33.3
Cold insert 1	1044.0	1876.0
Cold insert 2	877.0	877.0
Cold insert 3	1348.0	1348.0
Cold insert 4	1216.0	1524.2*
Cold insert 5	958.0	958.0
Mean value	1088.6	1316.6
Standard deviation	171.7	368.5
Hot insert 1	2237.0	2317.5
Hot insert 2	2077.0	2221.0
Hot insert 3	1761.0	2049.3*
Hot insert 4	1524.0	1524.0
Hot insert 5	1681.0	2009.5
Mean value	1856.0	2024.3
Standard deviation	262.3	274.2

*Pull-out force exceeds clamping force

Table 1: Force at first failure and maximum force for cylinder pull-out specimens

It can be seen that the standard deviations are bigger for the composite inserts than for the steel inserts. One reason for this observation is the differences in surface roughness of the uCF-PEEK inserts. Furthermore, the adherence between the insert and the overmould is highly dependent on the insert temperature. Two significant heat fluxes can be identified which influence the bonding strength.

On the one hand the hot inserts cool rapidly if they are transferred to the injection moulding machine. On the other hand the cold inserts are heated as soon as they are placed in the relatively hot tool of 215 °C. Since differences in the interface strength between the cold and hot specimens exist, it can be concluded that the heat transfer of the molten mass with a temperature of 400 °C is not enough to melt the surface of the cold inserts. Increasing the temperature of the molten mass in the injection moulding machine would increase the probability that the insert surface melts also at lower pre-heating temperatures and a cohesive interface is formed. However, it cannot be chosen higher since the material would degrade rapidly.

Due to thermal contraction, the overmoulded material applies some pressure on the insert surface. The thermal strain ε_T is defined by

$$\varepsilon_T = \alpha \Delta T, \quad (1)$$

in which α is the thermal expansion coefficient and ΔT is the temperature difference [4]. With the mean thermal expansion coefficients from the manufacturer [16] ($40 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ in the temperature range lower than T_g and $100 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ in the temperature range higher than T_g), thermal strain of the sCF-PEEK material is calculated with approximately 2.5 % for a cooling step from 343 °C to room temperature. By FEA, the contact pressure which is applied from the sCF-PEEK cylinder to the uCF-PEEK rod is determined. For faster convergence, the interaction between insert and overmould is modelled with a friction coefficient of 0.2. Considering the conservative scenario of a rod insert at room temperature, a contact pressure of about 150 MPa is achieved by thermal contraction of the hot overmould. The pressure is evenly distributed over the whole overlap region. Considering the assumption that the insert shows a pre-heating temperature of 250 °C and no cohesive bond is formed, there is no contact pressure. The uCF-PEEK rod shrinks more in the direction perpendicular to the endless fibres than the randomly short fibre reinforced sCF-PEEK cylinder. This means that if the inserts' surface melts and a cohesive interface is formed, residual tensile stresses are present after cooling.

For the examination of the interface of a hot specimen, a stereo-microscope is used. After pulling the rod completely out of the cylinder, the cylinder is cut in half. The cylinder cut and the rod are examined with a stereo microscope. Figure 7 illustrates an image of the cylinder cut on the left and of the corresponding rod on the right.

Figure 7: Stereo microscope images of the cylinder cut (left) and the corresponding rod (right)

The image on the left shows a bunch of endless fibres which stick to the short fibre PEEK material of the cylinder. A detailed examination confirms that endless fibres remain embedded in the cylinder material. This finding underlines that a cohesive interface between the uCF-PEEK material of the pre-heated rod and sCF-PEEK material of the overmould is formed. Similarly, the rod surface is studied. Short carbon fibres on the rod surface are seen in the image on the right which implies cohesive failure. This explains a rough rod surface after test. In summary, a cohesive interface is formed if the rod is pre-heated up to 290 °C. Heating the rod up is necessary since the heat transfer from the molten material to the insert is not enough to melt the insert surface.

9 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Since no standard test method is available for testing the interface strength of hybrid material combinations, different test methods are used and compared in this study. To test the interface strength of a uCF-PEEK insert which is overmoulded with sCF-PEEK material, compression shear test specimens are prepared. Due to several preparation steps, specimens fail prior to testing. The interface strength is very weak although several inserts are pre-heated up to 250 °C. This test procedure is inappropriate due to the amount of specimen preparation steps after the production of hybrid plates. It is shown that the pre-heating temperature of 250 °C is not enough to achieve a cohesive bond.

Due to several disadvantages of the compression shear test, single lap shear test specimens are produced for interface characterization. Here, only few steps are needed to prepare the specimens for testing. These steps do not influence the interface. The test results show that at a pre-heating temperature of approximately 300 °C, the surface of the inserts melts and a cohesive interface is formed. In this case, the interface strength exceeds the strength of the sCF-PEEK material.

This knowledge is used for the manufacturing of the cylinder pull-out test specimens with hot inserts. Here, a small reinforcement structure with high structural mechanical properties is totally overmoulded with a cheaper moulding material. It is important to pre-heat the inserts at the highest temperature possible (avoiding degeneration). On the one hand the probability that the molten sCF-PEEK melts the surface of the uCF-PEEK insert increases with increasing pre-heating temperature. On the other hand the insert has to be manageable which means that it has to keep its shape during transfer to the injection moulding machine. The results confirm that higher shear stresses are achieved if the insert is heated up well above T_g . The thermal analysis of the cylinder pull-out specimens shows that shrinkage of the overmoulded cylinder contributes to contact pressure on inserts with pre-heating temperatures lower than approximately 200 °C. The thermal shrinkage leads to an increase in pull-out forces for the cold insert specimens. The overmoulded steel inserts show very low maximum pull-out forces. The surface of the insert is very smooth so there can be no micro mechanical bond with the molten composite material. In general, the maximum forces of the specimens with uCF-PEEK inserts are by far higher than for those with steel inserts, especially if the composite inserts are pre-heated. During injection, the sCF-PEEK molten material hits the insert perpendicularly and then flows along the insert longitudinal axis. This mould design is realised since it is less complex and cost efficient. However, the molten material is injected with a high pressure so that the composite inserts slightly bend. Due to this curvature and thermal stresses, there is a strong locking between insert and overmould during pull-out test after first failure. As a consequence, forces further increase after first failure and higher maximum forces are achieved. The shear stress at first failure is used as an indicator of the interface quality. At this stress level, cracks start to propagate along the interface.

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